

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

MANIFESTATIONS OF PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT SYNDROME AMONG SOCIAL WORKERS WORKING WITH INDIVIDUALS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES IN DAY ACTIVITY CENTERS

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Abstract

This article elucidates the manifestations of burnout syndrome among social workers engaged with individuals with intellectual disabilities and examines timely intervention strategies. Social workers often report psychophysiological symptoms, such as chronic fatigue, which affect both their professional and personal lives, along with reduced activity levels and a lack of energy. Additionally, they experience significant social and psychological symptoms, including high levels of stress and increased irritability. The study also highlights the diversity of existing preventive measures against professional burnout. Institutions commonly offer professional development training and supervision to their employees. Furthermore, social workers actively engage in self-care and well-being practices, such as participating in preferred activities, taking outdoor walks, or engaging in other physical activities, to mitigate the effects of burnout syndrome.

Keywords: burnout syndrome, intellectual disability, day center, social worker.

Introduction. Burnout syndrome was first described in 1974 by American psychoanalyst Herbert Freudenberger. He observed that professionals such as healthcare workers, police officers, and social workers, who work closely with people and provide assistance, are more prone than others to experience exhaustion and chronic fatigue, negatively impacting their productivity and quality of life (1). Historically, the concept and understanding of burnout syndrome originated from stress research focused on the well-being and health of professionals. Over time, burnout syndrome became widely recognized as a phenomenon linked to emotionally demanding professions that involve significant emotional responsibility. In recent years, burnout syndrome has gained increasing attention due to rising workplace stress and the fast-paced nature of modern work and life (2). An expanding body of research and literature now examines burnout syndrome, its effects on employees and organizations, and strategies for mitigating and overcoming its risks.

In the professional field of social work, discussions about burnout syndrome, its manifestations, and prevention are not new. Social service institutions, guided by EU-regulated normative documents (*such as the OSH Framework Directive (89/391/EEC) and the International Association of Schools of Social Work (IASSW) Ethics in Social Work*), along with the normative legal framework developed in Lithuania based on these guidelines, have established various formal and informal measures to protect employees from burnout, taking into account the nature of work with clients. The scientific discussion on this topic is extensive but remains insufficient. Foreign researchers such as Hombrados-Mendieta et. al (3), Neumann et. al (4), as well

as Elbarazi et.al (5), actively examine the manifestations, causes, and intervention methods of burnout syndrome, aiming to identify timely solutions for recognizing and preventing professional burnout. In Lithuania, the phenomenon of professional burnout in the social services sector has been studied by Gudžinskienė et al. (6). Despite ongoing research and preventive measures being implemented in practice, burnout syndrome remains a significant issue in both social work practice and the field of scientific inquiry. In their studies, Nagle et. al (7) Samusevica et al (8), as well as Tolutiene et. al (9), emphasize the importance of investigating burnout manifestations by differentiating research based on the nature of client work and the types of institutions. This approach allows for a more thorough identification of the early signs of burnout syndrome and enables the development of timely intervention strategies. Consequently, the research questions addressed in this thesis are: (1) How do the early signs of burnout syndrome manifest in social workers working with individuals with intellectual disabilities in a day activity center? (2) What preventive measures are effective in mitigating the risk of burnout syndrome?

Methodology. Research Methods: Analysis of scientific literature. **Data Collection Methods:** A quantitative research approach was employed using a written survey. **Data Analysis Method:** Statistical data analysis. **Characteristics of the Quantitative Sample:** The study population consisted of social workers employed in day activity centers, providing social services to individuals with intellectual disabilities, and possessing at least 3 years of professional experience. A total of 120 participants (n = 120) took part in the study. The average age of the respondents was 43 years, with an average of 11 years of professional experience. All

participants in the study were women. The research adhered to the ethical principles associated with quantitative research.

Professional Challenges Faced by Social Workers

For the majority of individuals, professional activity constitutes a significant aspect of life, as it occupies a substantial portion of their time. Thus, both the nature of the profession and the work environment have profound effects on a person's mental, physical, and emotional well-being (10). According to these authors, an imbalance between professional demands, emerging challenges, and available resources may result in a heightened risk of professional burnout. The current study investigated the challenges encountered by social workers within their professional teams. The results indicate that a significant proportion of social workers (43.33%) reported a lack of openness and effective communication among colleagues, which often leads to conflicts and disagreements. Gudžinskienė et al. (6) also highlight interpersonal challenges as critical factors contributing to burnout syndrome among social workers.

In the study, respondents identified inadequate support as the least significant issue within their teams (26.66%). However, half of the social workers surveyed cited the lack of information sharing as the most pressing challenge. Additionally, 41.66% of respondents noted insufficient mutual connections among colleagues as a significant issue, while 40% pointed to internal competition as a prevalent challenge. A smaller percentage (11.66%) mentioned gossip, lack of knowledge, and unprofessional communication among team members as persistent concerns. Notably, a minority (4.5%) indicated that they experience no significant challenges, reporting high levels of team satisfaction and collaborative problem-solving.

Social work is a profession requiring a high degree of adaptability and versatility, as practitioners assist clients in adjusting to their environments, integrating into communities, and enhancing their social functioning. This role often involves challenging tasks, as each client presents unique circumstances. Kavaliauskienė et al. (10) emphasizes that social workers engage with diverse social groups and clients, often confronting complex and conflicting situations that generate significant

stress and tension. The author further notes that interactions with clients and their environments, client advocacy, and collaboration with various institutions can cause emotional and physical strain, potentially leading to adverse psychological outcomes for the worker.

The study reveals that 41.66% of social workers perceive excessive workloads and disproportionate responsibility for clients as major challenges. Additionally, 33.33% of social work professionals identified the lack of support when working with individuals with intellectual disabilities as a critical issue. A majority of respondents also highlighted low client motivation as a primary challenge in their work, with half of the social workers indicating that performing tasks on behalf of clients to achieve faster results poses a significant challenge. Bubnys et al. (11) state that choosing the profession of a social worker and performing such duties, a person's motivation gains special significance: it helps to achieve a high professional level, valuing one's work as meaningful and striving for good results, aiming to motivate individuals with intellectual disabilities. Given the dynamic nature of social work, which continually evolves with new methods and practices, it is crucial for social workers to remain open to ongoing learning and professional development. According to Ballan et al. (12), continuous professional growth enhances both the quality and efficiency of social work. Despite these demands, the study found that concerns about insufficient knowledge and skills were relatively low among respondents (21.66%).

Manifestations of Professional Burnout

People whose professions involve caring for others, such as social workers, often deplete their positive emotional resources over time, experience stress, and struggle to cope with its consequences. If this state persists, complete physical and mental exhaustion may occur, affecting a person's motivation, attitude, and behavior (10). A study conducted by Makasheva et al. (13) professional burnout manifests as emotional exhaustion, a lack of energy, and a loss of interest in work, often leading to decreased productivity and motivation. This syndrome can arise from intense workloads, stressful conditions, the monotony of activities, or a lack of professional self-fulfillment.

Chart 1. Assessments of Psychophysiological Manifestations Experienced by Social Workers

The study results indicate that social workers most frequently report experiencing constant fatigue, occurring approximately 1-2 times per month, as one of the prevalent psychophysiological symptoms. This fatigue is evident not only in their professional activities (mean score: 3.08) but also manifests as reduced overall activity and energy levels (mean score: 3.07). Mikalauskas et. al. (14) define emotional exhaustion as a state of emotional overexertion and depletion of personal re-

sources, characterized by feelings of confusion, inadequacy in social interactions, diminished energy, and an inability to meet imposed demands.

Social workers also rated the frequency of other symptoms, such as headaches (mean score: 2.78), memory impairment (mean score: 2.57), sudden mood changes (mean score: 2.55), and difficulties with falling asleep (mean score: 2.42), relatively high.

The present study examined the social-psychological manifestations of professional burnout among social workers.

Chart 2. Assessments of Social-Psychological Manifestations Experienced by Social Workers

The results indicate that social work professionals most frequently experience elevated levels of work-related stress (mean score: 2.83) and increased irritability (mean score: 2.77). According to Makasheva et. al (13), work-related stress arises when the work environment demands significant energy, concentration, and emotional resources from the professional, which may exceed their capacity to perform their duties effectively. As a result, when individuals are unable to meet these demands, they experience stress. Participants in the study reported experiencing diminished motivation for their work (mean score: 2.65) and a sense of anxiety without a clear cause (mean score: 2.60). Concerns

about the quality of their work were reported slightly more than 1-2 times per half-year (mean score: 2.37). Additionally, feelings of self-doubt (mean score: 2.27), indifference toward work-related problems (mean score: 2.15), and perceiving negative future prospects in their professional roles (mean score: 2.12) were among the least frequently reported symptoms. Stočkus (15) identifies depersonalization as a critical manifestation of professional burnout, characterized by a detached and indifferent attitude toward others. This reaction is often a self-protective measure to avoid further emotional exhaustion and disappointment. However, the study's findings suggest that indifference to work-

related challenges and a pessimistic outlook are less common among social workers who work with individuals with intellectual disabilities.

In further examining the manifestations of professional burnout syndrome, the study aimed to assess the frequency with which social workers experience behavioral indicators of burnout.

Chart 3. Behavioral Manifestations of Professional Burnout

The results indicate that among these behavioral manifestations, social workers most commonly report a lack of motivation for their work (mean score: 2.58) and a tendency to focus on trivial tasks while postponing more important responsibilities (mean score: 2.48). Changes in a specialist's behavior can signal that they are experiencing difficulties and exhibiting signs of behavioral burnout. Sarisik et. al (16) highlight that individuals who evaluate themselves negatively, express dissatisfaction with their work, and struggle to complete assigned tasks experience reduced personal achievement and diminished motivation. This inability to effectively perform tasks leads to feelings of worthlessness, decreased task quality, and reduced self-confidence and perceived expertise.

The study's findings indicate that a lack of work motivation among social workers is the most prevalent behavioral manifestation of burnout, which, in turn, results in procrastination of essential tasks and an excessive focus on minor details. Beer et. al (17) found that employees under constant stress and challenging work conditions often resort to harmful habits as coping

mechanisms, which can have long-term negative effects on their health. However, this study revealed that only a very small proportion of social workers resort to such harmful habits or the use of intoxicating substances for relief (mean score: 1.53), marking it as the least frequent behavioral manifestation. Less commonly, social workers reported adopting a cynical attitude toward their work (mean score: 1.83) and blaming colleagues or supervisors for their failures (mean score: 1.80), with these behaviors occurring approximately 1-2 times per half-year.

Preventive Measures for Coping with Professional Burnout

Gudžinskienė et. al (6) assert that for an individual to remain healthy, satisfied, and efficient in their work, it is essential to provide not only conditions that ensure safety and health but also a work environment that fosters overall well-being. According to Šidlauskaitė-Stripeikienė et. al (18), prevention is a crucial aspect of social work, with benefits that extend across economic, societal, and individual levels in addressing the various challenges faced by society.

Chart 4. Preventive Measures Applied in Workplaces

During this study, social workers were surveyed regarding the preventive measures implemented in their workplaces. The majority of respondents indicated that the most common preventive strategies include employee training and supervision. Tolutienė et. al (9) emphasizes that employee training serves as an effective preventive measure, benefiting professionals both in their career development and personal lives. The acquisition of stress management skills enables specialists to cope more effectively with stressful situations, thereby reducing the risk of burnout. In research conducted by Abromaitienė (19), social workers and educators who participated in supervision sessions reported positive outcomes, such as gaining deeper self-awareness, understanding colleagues better, sharing experiences, receiving support, viewing situations from different perspectives, fostering a sense of unity in the work environment, finding renewed motivation, and increasing self-confidence.

Social workers in the current study reported that workplaces are less likely to organize active leisure activities and team engagement, with 45% of respondents indicating the availability of such measures. Additionally, 36.66% of respondents noted that their workplaces employ intervention strategies as a preventive approach to address burnout. However, less frequently implemented preventive measures include relaxation practices, psychological resilience training, and self-help

strategies (20%). Time management (18.33%) emerged as the least commonly utilized preventive measure for reducing burnout. Čiarnienė et. al (20) argue that time management is an effective preventive strategy, helping individuals set clear goals and prioritize their activities. Despite its benefits, social workers in this study reported that time management is among the least frequently applied strategies for preventing burnout in their workplaces. Notably, 1.60% of respondents indicated that no preventive measures are currently in place at their workplace.

After assessing the preventive measures implemented by workplaces, the study also explored how social workers take personal responsibility for self-care and the preventive strategies they apply to reduce their risk of professional burnout. Given that social work is particularly characterized by frequent exposure to negative situations and emotions—such as client counseling and managing stressful circumstances—specialists are often required to remain resilient and composed. Despite this, social workers must find appropriate ways to express and process these emotions. The prolonged accumulation of negative emotions, coupled with a lack of effective coping strategies, can eventually lead to adverse effects on both personal and professional well-being. Therefore, it is crucial that social workers receive support not only from their workplace but also develop self-care practices.

Chart 5. Preventive Measures Social Workers Apply to Themselves

The study revealed that social workers actively engage in self-help strategies, with one of the most common being participation in a favorite activity (68.33%). Over half of the respondents indicated that engaging in hobbies serves as a preventive measure, helping them disconnect from work-related stress. Additionally, physical exercise and spending time outdoors are frequently chosen methods for stress relief. Gudžinskiė et.al (9) highlights that having a hobby and experiencing relaxation through leisure activities can significantly reduce symptoms of professional burnout, emphasizes the importance of planning leisure activities as a preventive measure. This approach enables social work professionals to effectively manage their time and energy, maintain a healthy lifestyle, and achieve a balance between work and personal life.

A study by Stoćkus (15) confirmed the benefits of physical activity, especially walking in improving both leisure and work-related well-being. Also claims that meditation can help individuals calm their minds, stay present, and alleviate accumulated stress. In the current study, 58.33% social workers confirmed the benefits of physical activity, but reported infrequent use of meditation as a self-care measure, and they also rarely sought professional help. Other preventive measures utilized by social workers include listening to favorite music (48.33%), engaging in physical activities (40%), and attending events or concerts (38.33%). Additionally, some social workers reported using massage therapy (31.66%) and practicing meditation (21.66%) to mitigate the effects of burnout.

Conclusion. Burnout syndrome among social workers employed in day activity centers and working with individuals with intellectual disabilities is characterized by psychophysiological, social-psychological, and behavioral changes. The findings of the study reveal that psychophysiological symptoms are the most frequently reported. Participants highlighted chronic fatigue as a prevailing issue, negatively impacting both

their professional performance and personal lives. Additionally, they noted diminished energy levels and a reduced ability to engage in activities. Social-psychological manifestations of burnout were also prominent, with social workers frequently reporting high levels of stress and heightened irritability. Although behavioral symptoms were mentioned less frequently, they included a decline in work motivation, resulting in procrastination on critical tasks while prioritizing less important ones, which ultimately undermines work quality and productivity.

An analysis of existing preventive measures and the findings of this study indicate that institutions providing services to individuals with intellectual disabilities predominantly implement professional training and supervision as their main strategies to combat burnout syndrome. Conversely, self-help and time management practices were the least utilized institutional measures. Despite organizational efforts, social workers themselves actively adopt personal preventive strategies to maintain their well-being. The study highlights that many social workers frequently engage in activities they enjoy, spend time outdoors, or participate in physical exercises. These activities serve as effective methods to alleviate burnout symptoms, promote relaxation, and restore a sense of balance between their professional and personal lives.

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